

Species 1: *H. hecale*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.65; high PNT

NOT test

Species 2: *H. elevatus*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.27; moderate PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1

Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.426

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.266

p.value = 0.002

Background 2->1

D

p.value = 0.03846

Background 1->2

D

p.value = 0.01099

Species 1: *H. hecale*

NDT test

Species 2: *H. elevatus*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D = 0.273

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

